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Identification of key challenges and information needs of those enabling and implementing interactive innovation projects within the EIP-Agri

Enabling policies for Research and Innovation: governance, frameworks and pathways (conference topic 3)

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Abstract

The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-Agri) is a relatively new policy concept that aims to speed up innovation in agriculture and forestry. Our paper presents key challenges and information needs of (potential) beneficiaries, advisors, support services, educators, policy makers and administrators. Since the EIP-Agri aims to address the needs of various stakeholders and to foster projects on the regional, national and European level, its implementation is complex. Our analysis is based on data obtained at workshops that took place in Northern, South-Eastern, Southern and North-Western Europe in November 2018. Each workshop followed a common script and reporting guideline leaving space to account for the diverse macro-regional contexts. While the heterogeneity within each macro-region was high, the results show that i) the particular institutional settings impact on the enhancement of farmer-led networks/projects, ii) economic incentives either drive or hamper the involvement, iii) fore-runners in the field of interactive innovation exist in both policy/administration and in practice, iv) the maturity of administrative systems is of great relevance and impacts significantly on the cooperation and co-creation of stakeholders. This paper contributes to the knowledge exchange and co-learning between practitioners, advisors, scientists, and representatives from policy and administration in Europe who are aiming for interactive innovation in agricultural, forestry and rural value chains. The comments and recommendations collected at the ESEE 2019 conference will feed into the further work of the LIAISON project.

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Introduction

The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-Agri) is a policy concept which aims to speed up innovation in agriculture and forestry through linking existing policies and instruments (EC, 2013). This concept is based on the idea that mixed groups of farmers, advisors, researchers, entrepreneurs and educators (innovation actors) work together to develop innovative solutions for farming, forestry and the related rural supply chains. The EIP-Agri concept is part of the European Union's (EU) policy framework to fund various types of European or local-level projects or networks which are based on the so-called interactive innovation approach. The idea of this approach is to enhance cooperation and coordination of different types of actors to make best use of their complementary types of knowledge and by this foster co-creation and diffusion of ready-to-use solutions.

With this paper, we aim to analyse the current challenges of those enabling and maintaining interactive innovation projects and networks under the current EIP-Agri framework. By addressing these challenges we aim to contribute to fostering co-learning and knowledge exchange between scientists, advisors and representatives from policy and administration in Europe and help to improve the implementation of the EIP-Agri concept. A first attempt is made to provide recommendations on how to address these challenges.

The analysis is mainly based on a multi-stakeholder consultation process in four European geographical macro-regions. The following sections present the multi-stakeholder

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approach, highlight the identified challenges and conclude with some preliminary recommendations.

Methodology

In challenging contexts, such as the EU, where the diverse expectations of stakeholders from the public, policy and science meet, (successful) scientific assessments must simultaneously address questions of policy relevance, scientific quality and legitimacy (Engels, 2005). In this realm, scientists are confronted with many new questions and expectations such as a growing demand for participatory approaches (ibid.). The importance of public participation in political processes has received increasing attention and led to ample research on stakeholder analysis and integration (Alves Zanella et al., 2018; Klerkx et al., 2017; Hermans et al., 2015; Reed et al., 2009).

While different methods are available for i) identifying stakeholders, ii) differentiating between and categorising stakeholders and iii) investigating relationships between stakeholders (Reed et al., 2009), most projects and purposes require all these steps and some methods may even be used for more than one purpose. In general, it must be considered which approaches, stakeholders and actor constellations will contribute to an effective and efficient discussion (ibid.). Furthermore, research on participatory approaches, such as science-policy-interfaces (Engels, 2005) or multi-stakeholder deliberation platforms (Garard et al., 2018), and in particular, on cooperation for agricultural innovation (Cristiano et al., 2017) has shown that they are best regarded as continuous processes rather than isolated

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events. Consequently, to ensure trust amongst participants, these processes need structuring so that meetings can and will be repeated.

Based on this methodological background, a forum for a facilitated continuous dialogue in four European macro regions ('LIAISON macro-regional hubs') brings together actors involved in the LIAISON project¹ and stakeholders from neighbouring countries, which have complementary expertise and roles in the field of interactive innovation in agriculture, forestry and the bioeconomy. The LIAISON members leading the macro-regional hubs act like 'brokers for information demands and supplies' (FAO, 1995) while taking into account the relevance of geographical proximity (Cristiano et al., 2017) and the different contexts of countries and regions (Klerkx et al., 2017; Hermans et al., 2015).

This macro-regional approach aims to i) take into account the regional contexts (i.e. cultural, economic, political and social aspects), ii) have a multiplying function among those involved and iii) link transition and western-European countries for cross-border cooperation and learning. A stakeholder mapping process (inspired by Social Network Analysis and Knowledge Mapping discussed by Reed et al. (2009), guided the selection of the participants of the LIAISON macro-regional workshops (MRWS), which were held in the 'Danube-Balkan', 'Mediterranean', 'North-West' and 'Nordic-Baltic' macro-regions. All workshops followed a common script and reporting guideline, which left space to account for the groups' diverse contexts and requirements. Tools such as break-out groups, tour-de-table and plenary

¹ LIAISON is a multi-actor research and innovation project funded under the framework of the EU Horizon 2020 programme (Grant agreement no 773418); www.liaison2020.eu.

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discussion sessions were used, adjusted to the different groups including their positions and focal points to avoid a ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach (Klerkx et al., 2017) and to ensure maximum output.

A review of academic and policy-oriented literature on the EIP-Agri policy concept and participative approaches for innovation in agriculture and forestry provided the basic understanding of the policy framework, the requirements of innovation groups and guided the development of the key questions to be addressed.

The target group and envisaged end-users of the findings from the stakeholder consultation process and the desk-based studies are not only the selected participants but in general, potential beneficiaries of Horizon 2020 projects, groups supported by the Rural Development Programmes (RDP) such as Operational Groups (OG), national and regional programming and support agencies (policy makers, administrators, rural networks etc.), other innovation project facilitators and advisors, EU and non-EU institution representatives and others who engage in the interactive innovation project approach. These groups are seen as ‘those enabling and implementing interactive innovation projects within the EIP-Agri’.

Challenges and information needs identified

The challenges are various, some result from lacking experiences or difficult administrative processes of the relatively-new funding and programming of the policy concept, others emerge from the complexity of group or management processes and the heterogeneity of interactive innovation. Moreover, challenges derive from the different strategies, commitments and priorities around the areas of achievement. Operational issues already

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experienced by the early adopters (2013-2015) (Member States (MS), regions or networks themselves) of the interactive innovation network approach, are often being encountered now by later adopters in the current phase. The following sections present some areas of persistent concern.

Governance and participation in interactive innovation

The institutional arrangements of EU MS are often very different. For example, the role and place of Ministries of Agriculture and their regional services may reveal much about how agricultural innovation pathways have been, and can be, constructed and adapted. Although widely spread in ministries and administration of the EU MS, the involvement of multi-level actors is still often insufficient (MRWS Danube-Balkan, 2019). In some contexts, agricultural unions as well as state institutions tend to seek the maintenance of existing structures and procedures, and are sometimes reluctant to consider, or participate in, more radical or innovative structural realignments around local, networked initiatives (MRWS Mediterranean, 2019). However, project fatigue and building down of institutions may also be part of the context (ibid.)

In general, stakeholders observed that farmers and locals are often easier to motivate to engage in interactive innovation projects than institutional partners, in particular in local-level projects or networks. Distinct incentives (especially financial ones) can raise farmers' interest and offer strong reasons for participation. In contrast, the motivation and involvement of institutions is challenging because they tend to have established structures which require

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time and motivation to adapt (MRWS Mediterranean, Nordic-Baltic, North-West, Danube-Balkan, 2019).

Experiences from large EU-funded Horizon 2020 research consortia show that the direct involvement of farmers in such structures can also be problematic. The participation of farmers and farmers' groups in such projects is generally only sustainable if the research offers genuine gains, usually in the form of specific applicable solutions to known problems, best-practice examples, or specific and durable assistance in the trialling, testing and upscaling of innovative practices and technologies. Sometimes articulating research outputs for these end-user groups is very challenging (MRWS Nordic-Baltic, North-West, 2019).

Variations are particularly noticeable across countries with different traditions of agricultural advisory services and support (SCAR-AKIS, 2018). In the forthcoming funding period, MS and/or regions will develop AKIS Strategic Plans² as required by the EC which will feed in the RDP for the period 2021-2028. Many MS, especially in north-western European countries, have well-developed publicly-funded agricultural advisory services. Since these are seen as core drivers for the AKIS (PRO AKIS, 2018), representatives from those countries with strong publicly-funded advisory systems such as France, Ireland, Belgium and Poland are very active in the SCAR-AKIS. However, there are as well countries without strong advisory services in north-western Europe (e.g. Sweden or some German

² Under the framework of the next RDP 2021-2028, EU MS must establish strategic plans for the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in the country (Van Oost 2018).

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Federal States) as well as in other regions. These areas with mainly private or less-structured farm advisory structures are less present in the policy field (MRWS North-West 2019).

Stakeholder discussions highlight that, in a broader sense, the interactive innovation approach needs to encourage more industry partners (not just small/medium sized enterprises ‘SMEs’) to join multi-actor groups, networks and projects (MRWS North-West, Mediterranean, 2019). Industrial and commercial partners may be key partners in innovation processes, particularly as ‘multipliers’ to assist in the wider adoption and diffusion (and possibly commercialisation) of innovations. However, such partners often need to see concrete, commercial benefits in order to justify joining a project group. Unlike for other types of partners, project funding is unlikely to be an incentive on its own – an attractive business model for the exploitation of results might be a better incentive. However, there is an inevitable tension between the obligation to share results and their results. This tension increases in projects that are near-market, especially competitive markets for new technologies (Redman, 2018).

The diversity and inherent multi-functionality of cooperatives and producer associations offers considerable potential and real opportunities for enhancing interactive innovation where such bodies can be brought to support collective actions. Examples and best-practice accounts of where such support has been forthcoming could be recognised and shared. Current ‘champions of innovations’ are often unknown or rarely ‘officially’ acknowledged (MRWS North-West, 2019).

Although farmers lie at the centre of the EIP-Agri initiative, often farmers and other agricultural stakeholders, even if members of an OG, do not see themselves as integrated

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components of the wider EIP-Agri or Horizon 2020 concept (MRWS North-West, 2019). Many of the currently-active OGs target specific farm-level issues and avoid the ‘distraction’ from the wider institutional and funding context, which indicates that the wider impact of the EIP-Agri and its networking potential over and above the establishment of individual and isolated networks is not being fully realised.

Re-joining observations made in an evaluation of the implementation of the EIP-Agri (Fotheringham et al., 2016) and others, Kah and Gruber (2018) identified a lack of interconnectivity between EIP-Agri and other relevant policy areas. Although the links between the EIP-Agri and Horizon 2020 are explicit and well developed, the place of the EIP-Agri within other related policy areas and debates is potentially under-developed, particularly when such links might be advantageously explored to overcome barriers to innovation (Fotheringham et al., 2016; Kah and Gruber, 2018).

Multi-actor initiatives, bringing together commercial actors, scientists and others, inevitably raise the important issue of the ownership of project outcomes, which becomes all the more significant when those outcomes either are commercially sensitive or have direct economic value. Redman (2018) highlights the need for more guidance on implementing Horizon 2020 policy on Open Access to Research Data. There is ambiguity and uncertainty around the EC's approach of ‘*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*’ and a clearer understanding is required of how to opt out of open access and instead keep results with commercial value in the group.

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Management and financial administration of interactive innovation projects

Some specific concerns emerge from the management of Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects: the involvement of stakeholders who are not direct beneficiaries of project resources, in particular when other stakeholders are consortium partners and receive funding for their work. There are pros and cons for the payment of practice partners or SMEs who contribute directly to the project but who may also profit directly from the project activities and outputs (MRWS Nordic-Baltic, 2019). More advice from the EC would help to establish guidelines that project consortia could use as a commonly-agreed procedure (Redman, 2018).

A further concern is duplication and overlap. Several research projects funded under Horizon 2020 cover very similar topics. However, linking projects is time consuming and requires a specific management task. Project managers would need clearer guidelines, and support in this area (Redman, 2018).

The administrative burdens of engagement in interactive innovation networks, OGs or thematic research networks can be significant, especially for small enterprises or voluntary associations. The financial mechanisms employed and the risks of non-compliance with legal and financial rules sometimes discourage the engagement of participants or of those responsible for administering the project or network (MRWS North-West, Danube-Balkan, Mediterranean, 2019). More training of decision makers of financial administration or financial control agencies could help to improve acceptance and trust in the new funding schemes, e.g. in Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries (MRWS Danube-Balkan, 2019). Knowledge exchange between EIP-Agri forerunners and late starters is very much appreciated by participants in cross-border seminars (Seminar EIP-Agri, 2018). However, the

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knowledge transfer between administrative staff between regions cannot always work. Structural differences with either commercial or small family farms in CEE MS needs specific consideration. Stakeholders from the Baltic Sea area, and specifically from Poland, pointed out that the decision makers, although fully acknowledging the regional diversity of agriculture/forestry, are not taking into account the structural differences with either very large industrial or very small family farms when designing a target-oriented policy. As a result, national policies and support measures are often not effective for innovation and interaction in terms of addressing the specific needs in the rural areas or particular industries (i.e. the same measures cannot apply for both semi-subsistence family farms and professionally-managed commercial farms) (MRWS Danube-Balkan, 2019).

In particular, the involvement of the courts of audits and their understanding (and support for) the mechanisms of interactive innovation processes has been highlighted as a significant challenge by many stakeholders (MRWS North-West, 2019; Seminar EIP-Agri, 2018). The funding rules and their implementation depend on the experiences of both the administrative organisations and individual officers (MRWS Danube-Balkan and North-West, 2019).

In a variety of contexts, the financial rules and procedures associated with the active promotion and support of interactive innovation, whether through RDPs, OGs, EIP-Agri or Horizon 2020 are seen as a constraint to participation and engagement.

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Design and selection of project proposals

Our analysis identifies several issues around the design and submission of innovation network proposals, OG applications or Horizon 2020 research proposals. The availability of ‘seed funding’ to help prepare project proposals can encourage the target group of beneficiaries to overcome this challenging period (MRWS North-West, Nordic-Baltic, 2019). Smaller organisations or researchers not familiar with Horizon 2020 may particularly benefit (Münchhausen, 2018). Some authorities apply a two-step procedure which helps applicants to go through the proposal development process. Experiences from programmes in e.g. Latvia and Germany show that the project plans were greatly improved during the second phase.

The EIP-Agri mandate embraces a wide range of agricultural and rural contexts. However, the decision of which pathways to innovation are suitable for support and funding under the RDPs is not always well defined (MRWS Danube-Balkan, North-West, Mediterranean, 2019). Guidelines from well-established selection processes in specific countries could help both less-experienced managing authorities and those considering applying for support (MRWS Nordic-Baltic, 2019). The value of learning from good practice and experience of others was a key message taken from the discussions with authorities, farmer groups and other rural actors at the Seminar EIP-Agri (2018).

For all funding schemes, a major concern is that many of the concerns relating to agriculture, its role in the rural economy and the wider context of food and environmental security are not being addressed by the different innovation-driving initiatives (e.g. MRWS Mediterranean, 2019). Innovations that emerge from OGs may have substantive impact at the local scale on the day-to-day business. However, practitioners tend to be oblivious of

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emerging problems that might require future-oriented solutions. While innovation is undoubtedly required at this level, the EIP-Agri could also stimulate, drive and disseminate innovation for a broader and more far-reaching set of objectives (MRWS North-West, 2019).

Evaluation and impact assessment of interactive innovation projects and networks

Innovation means different things to different actors, sectors and processes. For that reason, the selection criteria for projects and the subsequent evaluation or impact assessment procedures are important tools for steering the EIP-Agri and the development of innovation projects. Differences between European regions and MS are apparent. Those directing agricultural/forestry innovation policy in north-western and Scandinavian countries tend to be aware of the impact of organisational or social innovation while funding programmes in CEE countries concentrate more on technical innovation (MRWS Danube-Balkan, Mediterranean, North-West, Nordic-Baltic, 2019). Such variations require further investigation.

Similarly, the assessment and evaluation of an innovation's impact, and therefore viability, also presents challenges when observed across different contexts. How to assess when innovation is achieved? Innovations can have a greater impact in some agricultural/forestry sectors than others leading to possible biases in the nature and function of the innovation groups. Stakeholders pointed out the potential for 'increasing the gap' between those able to take advantage of these innovation efforts, and those not (MRWS Nordic-Baltic, 2018). The assessment of the impact of an innovation network is challenging because the delivery or performance is often difficult to measure (SCAR, 2018), several factors drive the development of innovation and the changes are not easily linked to only one project or

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initiative. More guidance is needed for the use of qualitative or quantitative evaluation procedures that are fit for the purpose of developing interactive innovative solutions.

Communication, dissemination and exploitation

While Fotheringham et al. (2016) draw attention to the success of the EIP-Agri concept and to the growth of OGs emanating from national RDPs, particularly in establishing a distinctive and transformative culture for innovation within European agriculture and agricultural support, they also identify limitations in the broader integration of both the OGs as a mechanism and EIP-Agri as a framework. The community of people conversant with the activities and outputs offered by the EIP-Agri services is growing but still limited.

It is a challenge to promote and encourage the reporting and dissemination of experiences and good practice examples beyond projects' immediate communities of interest, and particularly beyond the distinct policy communities of agriculture, forestry and rural development (Redman, 2018). The development of practical guidelines for the reporting on both the lessons learned from the technical or organisational innovation (the content) and from the cooperation process within the group of mixed actors is still a challenge (Seminar EIP-Agri, 2018). For example, the databases which provide access to Practice Abstracts and to other outputs still lack visibility for end-users (MRWS Danube-Balkan, Mediterranean, North-West, and Nordic-Baltic, 2019).

Moreover, the publications are often written by persons who are heavily involved in the specific context of EIP-Agri and lack the required distance for the use of a common language with terminology that would be used by end-users or the general public. Translation

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into national languages is another well-known challenge. Results need to be available in national languages because end-users often do not use English but translations are resource intensive. These are concerns which require new approaches (MRWS Daube-Balkan, Mediterranean, 2019).

Dissemination activities need to be well planned and often require more time than expected. Since resources required for dissemination have often been underestimated in interactive innovation projects, and the diffusion of innovations resulting has not always been evident, it is important to allow enough time and budget and for a longer period before the end of the project. This is an issue that needs to be addressed during planning and grant agreement development (Seminar EIP-Agri 2018; MRWS North-West. 2019).

Although required and often discussed, the continuation of the networks and assembled communities of practice after the end of the funding period of a project is a significant challenge. Coordination requires resources which often cease at the end of the supported period. Good examples show that links with businesses and local enterprises, economic associations, training/learning or volunteer networks can be useful in maintaining the cooperation among stakeholders in the area or the sector. Economic clusters, multipliers and established networks as well as cooperatives can also ensure financial means for the continuation of the network (MRWS North-West 2019).

Finally, flexibility and creativity in communication and dissemination are key requisites for innovative interactions to take place, as experts from the Mediterranean area highlighted (MRWS Mediterranean, 2019). Moreover, long-term support is important. To secure this, additional funding for information, dissemination/training may well be needed.

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Such funding could relate to the particular project and represent an extension of a payment beyond the termination of the project. Alternatively, independent funding programmes for the communication of the results from finalised projects might ensure such activities (MRWS North-West, 2019).

Effective networks and the effective dissemination of innovations often rely on shared ownership particularly among those actors who are at the origin of the innovation or who have established innovative business models. With the requirement of Open Access to all results of the projects, ownership and (exclusive) economic use of the innovation is an issue for many private enterprises when they do not wish to participate in publicly-funded projects (MRWS Nordic-Baltic, 2019).

Identification of key areas for further discussion

In this section, we cluster key areas for discussion which aim to support the further development of the EIP-Agri concept. The three key areas for future research and development highlight issues relating to the functioning and support of interactive, multi-actor innovation networks both in terms of ground-level OG and Horizon 2020 consortia:

- Economic incentives for farmers/foresters and entrepreneurs from the supply chain;
- Role of advisors and advisory organisations in the implementation of the EIP-Agri;
- Impact of the maturity of administrative systems on funding rules and procedures.

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Role of economic incentives for farmers/foresters and entrepreneurs from the supply chain

Farmers, foresters and processing organisations are – for various reasons – often difficult to involve in interactive innovation projects. For them, entrepreneurial concerns and expectations have an impact upon the potential engagement in interactive innovation activities. Any such engagement in the development or testing of innovation is likely to be time consuming for the individuals involved, especially when additional tasks of coordination, communication and reporting are required as is the case for interactive innovation processes and group or network projects.

At the same time, the effective use and dissemination of innovations often depend on the degree of shared ownership, particularly among those actors who are at the origin of the innovation or who have established innovative business models. Addressing these inherent tensions is a necessary step in advancing the contribution of Horizon 2020. Multi-actor projects thereby require specific ‘models’ of consortium agreement, with particular emphasis on balancing commercial and scientific interests.

The farming and forestry sectors in many MS are characterised by the significant role played by professional organisations, whether trade unions, cooperatives or producer groups, who represent their members across a variety of policy areas. Enhancing interactive innovation initiatives often requires significant support from such bodies. Their role in promoting innovation (or indeed in hindering innovation and the initiatives that might support it, whether directly or indirectly) needs to be examined more closely.

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Role of advisors and advisory organisations in the implementation of the EIP-AGRI

Many OG and Horizon 2020 projects have provided strong evidence to show how multi-actor innovation networks work. Research and activities undertaken under both funding schemes have drawn in individual farmers/foresters, established groups such as producer organisations, cooperatives and local farmers' unions along with advisors, commercial partners and facilitators. This has largely been achieved through innovative and flexible funding streams, financial agreements and rules. Flexibility within the different RDPs has been an important component of this. This flexibility has accompanied, and assisted, a greater diversification of actors, from agriculture/forestry, from science and research and from the myriad bodies and structures that facilitate and multiply innovation. This diversification, which has brought new actors and new agendas to the table, is to be strongly welcomed.

The integration of advisory services in the EIP-Agri at the regional level is a central factor of success for interactive innovation in many regions. In countries or regions with strong networks of advisory bodies (e.g. Teagasc in Ireland), such organisations are involved in many projects at different levels, and play a key supporting role, alongside farmers and their representatives, in innovation networks. In some cases, advisory bodies have coordinated individual networks. The prominence of a strong AKIS in the many of the north-western European countries/regions often coincides with a strong and well-embedded advisory service presence, as demonstrated in the findings of the Horizon 2020 project PRO AKIS (2018). Accompanying this are a cohort of well-educated farmers and a well-developed support infrastructure for agricultural operations. In some north-west European regions, it is very much these factors that have contributed significantly to the establishment of OG and uptake

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of the interactive innovation approach. In short, these areas, mainly in the north-west of the EU, would appear to have some of the best conditions for innovation and investment, linked undoubtedly to their economic strength, climate and population density with an increasingly more diverse agriculture. PRO AKIS (2018) argues that the existence of strong advisory systems is a key driver of AKIS in the countries/regions. Therefore, it is expected that the AKIS strategy plans will envisage to foster further the position of the advisory institutions (SCAR-AKIS, 2018). Future developments will reveal the roles that these well-established advisory organisations will play, and how interactive innovation will progress in those areas that do not have a tradition of robust advisory structures.

Impact of the maturity of administrative systems on funding rules and procedures

Since in a variety of contexts the financial rules and procedures are seen as a constraint to participation and engagement, many stakeholders emphasised that their reform and simplification will be critical and necessary for the optimisation of these policy instruments. For the first set of interactive innovation projects, the approval and administration has been challenging for emergent OG and for the relevant authorities because cost reimbursement and control processes are substantively different from the financial administration of farm investment or agri-environmental schemes. However, areas that introduced the EIP-Agri funding scheme procedures some time ago show that payments are processed smoothly and controls in place work well. This is a significant achievement in many countries and regions, notably those that started early with the programming and publication of interactive innovation policy support policies under the RPD, those in the north-west European macro-

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region such as Germany, the Netherlands, France, Sweden and Belgium. Other countries that began later with implementing EIP-Agri are still learning how to administer the framework efficiently and in a supportive way the OG projects.

We might also ask whether the maturity of administrative systems in the ministries of agriculture and in other sectors of national or regional government and administration has impacted on the potential to introduce the new schemes in support of interactive innovation. When the application procedures for OG were introduced, managing authorities in north-western MS insisted on the establishment of a legally-defined unit of beneficiaries for the innovation project. However, this has been subsequently identified as a barrier because the processes for the legal registration of a working group aiming for OG status consumed time and money at a point in time when the innovation project has not yet been funded. In response, several administering authorities changed these requirements to a consortium agreement or cooperation contract and the formation of a legal unit is no longer compulsory. This was an example of quick changes in the funding rules that facilitated the approval of projects.

Funding authorities often require strict rules in place because they fear the legal consequences of non-compliance. In the case of rural development initiatives, this is often compounded by a limited understanding among authority personnel of the new rules and circumstances surrounding the mechanisms for promoting interactive innovation. More training of decision makers and controllers in the financial administration could help to improve acceptance and trust in the new funding schemes for innovation groups or networks. This is relevant for all administrative levels; regional, national and European public

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administration and financial policy. The knowledge exchange between EIP-Agri forerunners and late starters in EIP-Agri implementation has been shown to be highly appreciated by staff who participated in the Seminar EIP-Agri (2018).

Responsible administrators in charge of public spending in the MS and EU regions play a significant role in agreeing financial support and in managing the cost claims of beneficiaries. This issue is well known and regularly discussed by beneficiaries in the context of factors hampering EIP-Agri implementation. However, it is difficult to assess how exactly, and to what extent, the financial administration of managing authorities and the control function of the courts of audit behind them impacts on the success of interactive innovation approaches. Policy programmers and administrators of RDPs tend to emphasise the importance of personal contacts between personnel of the various authorities involved. Round tables or joint working groups for officers of the different organisations can help to build a common understanding and to facilitate grant negotiations and the financial administration of interactive innovation projects.

Conclusion

The aim of the paper was to identify key challenges of those engaged in interactive innovation in the fields of agriculture, food, forestry and the bioeconomy. Since a stakeholder consultation identified and analysed these challenges in and for different geographical macro-regions, it was possible to acknowledge the ‘general’ cultural, historical and structural background in the areas. Results show that this approach was suitable for the identification and the clustering of key areas of concern. Although the heterogeneity within each macro-

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region was high, the approach allowed the inclusion of countries' or societies' specificities more than with a pan-European approach without losing the overall picture when looking at the regional level.

We conclude with an identification of leading questions for the discussion at the ESEE conference and for the further engagement in the development of the EIP-Agri concept:

- The different institutional configurations in the countries/regions play a key role for the enhancement of farmer-led networks that are fundamentally different from more traditional forms of farmer representation. How to identify and explore the differences of such institutional configurations effectively?
- Economic incentives for the different types of stakeholders drive or hamper the involvement in the EIP-Agri. How to give guidance for the implementation of the Horizon 2020 policy on Open Access to Research Data when entrepreneurs aim for competitive advantages of their businesses and unique selling points?
- There are forerunners in the field of interactive innovation in policy/administration and in practice. How to recognise, share and 'officially acknowledge' best-practice examples and 'champions of innovations'?
- EU policy will foster advisory services specifically because of their central role in the AKIS of many MS. Which groups of organisations or stakeholders will grow into this role of innovation facilitator and knowledge broker in those areas that do not have strong (semi-)public advisory institutions? And how to support these?
- The maturity of administrative systems in the different countries/regions is relevant, but how to encourage joint learning, networking and inter-organisational cooperation?

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